

High-Precision and High-Accuracy Copper Nuclear Data for Fast Reactor Analyses

D. M. Castelluccio^{1,2,*}, A. Berardi^{2,3}, P. Console Camprini^{1,2}, G. Grasso¹, C. Massimi^{2,3},
A. Musumarra^{4,5}, M. G. Pellegriti⁵, N. Pieretti^{1,3}, A. Talamazzini³

¹ENEA, via dei Mille 21, Bologna, Italy; ²INFN, viale C. Berti Pichat 6/2, Bologna, Italy;

³University of Bologna, DIFA, via Irnerio 46, Bologna, Italy;

⁴University of Catania, piazza Università 2, Catania, Italy; ⁵INFN, via Santa Sofia 64, Catania, Italy

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ABSTRACT

The accuracy of nuclear data is a key requisite for achieving optimized performance in designing nuclear systems. For operating reactors, return of experience is generally used to augment differential measurements; it means that, for reactors of novel technologies, alternative means are to be found. For fast spectrum reactors, the RSV TAPIRO - a hard-spectrum zero-power research reactor operated by ENEA at the Casaccia Research Center near Rome — could play a central role. A peculiarity of TAPIRO is the thick copper reflector, which influences the core performance. A thorough study of the sensitivity and uncertainty of key neutronic parameters due to copper cross sections was therefore conducted, to appreciate the impact of these data on the representativeness of experiments to target fast reactor designs. The findings motivated the RAMEN initiative, launched within the Euratom-funded APRENDE project. RAMEN involves an experimental campaign at the n_TOF facility at CERN aimed at refining copper evaluations. Capture and total cross-section measurements have already been completed, with data reduction currently in progress. In parallel, feasibility studies have established the path toward future elastic and inelastic scattering measurements using stilbene scintillation detectors. These coordinated efforts will ultimately lead to improved copper evaluations, enabling TAPIRO to express at best its potential in support to advanced fast reactors.

Keywords: Copper; Nuclear data; Fast-spectrum; TAPIRO; n_TOF

1. THE STRATEGIC ROLE OF TAPIRO FOR FAST REACTOR DEVELOPMENT

The optimization of the design of reactor cores requires high-quality and comprehensive nuclear data to ensure accurate neutronic analyses, so to secure that robust safety margins are properly set, which minimize undue operational penalties. After decades of continuous nuclear data improvement, the main sources of uncertainties presently derive, chiefly, from poor nuclear data of isotopes of secondary importance, and even more from the residual uncertainties on the data of the main isotopes. By means of differential measurements, for the former wide margins exist for improvement; conversely, for the latter, the residual uncertainties may be extremely challenging to reduce, being often at the frontier of the experimental errors even with the most sophisticated devices. A standard practice to overcome this issue is to combine differential measurements with the results of integral tests, provided that representative reactors (including experimental ones) are available. When dealing with fast reactors, however, the limited availability of operating reactors might impair walking this alternative route. Within this framework, the RSV TAPIRO research reactor, operated by ENEA at the Casaccia Research Center, near Rome, constitutes an invaluable unique asset: indeed, TAPIRO is a compact, zero-power reactor sustaining a hard spectrum in the whole reactor and an almost pure fission spectrum in the

*Corresponding author: donato.castelluccio@enea.it

center of the core. For its extremely well characterized neutron spectrum, TAPIRO is able to act both as a general-purpose fast-neutron source and a reference benchmark reactor for the integral validation of nuclear data and innovative fast-spectrum systems.

Historically, TAPIRO has served as a key facility for validating nuclear data and computational methods in fast-reactor applications, supporting shielding studies, cross section adjustments, and detector qualification. Relevant activities in the past were about shielding and propagation studies in sodium and steel-sodium mixtures for the Superphénix reactor. Experimental data and related analyses conducted in the development of the consistent method for reconciling energy-dependent and integral data [1] and later in the AMARA+ code [2], designed to optimize cross sections within experimental uncertainties. The versatility of TAPIRO was recently reaffirmed during the international AOSTA campaign [3], which confirmed the feasibility of improving minor actinide data through integral irradiations.

For TAPIRO to continue serving first class experimental results in an ever improving world, a broad collaboration was recently established, specifically focused to the improvement of copper cross sections to further enhance the representativeness of TAPIRO benchmarks to fast reactor applications. In fact, the metallic core of TAPIRO is surrounded by a thick copper reflector, with reactivity controlled by rods, made of copper as well. The use of copper as the reflecting material makes the reactor particularly sensitive to the quality of copper nuclear data, yet fundamental for the interpretation of benchmark experiments.

Despite advances in major libraries, copper isotopes (^{63}Cu , ^{65}Cu) still suffer from inconsistent evaluations and a limited, partly outdated experimental basis, leading to observable effects on calculated quantities such as k_{eff} and spectral indices. Recent studies conducted by ENEA with ERANOS and MCNP codes highlighted copper elastic, inelastic, and capture reactions as dominant factors impacting the quality and representativeness of integral observables when current nuclear data evaluations are used. Motivated by these findings, and aiming at strengthening the predictive capability in fast-spectrum conditions, the collaboration gathering ENEA, INFN and the CERN n.TOF (Neutron Time-Of-Flight) Collaboration launched the RAMEN initiative, as a coordinated experimental program within the Euratom-funded APRENDE project.

2. IMPACT OF COPPER EVALUATIONS ON TAPIRO AS A BENCHMARK

ENEA recently performed feasibility studies for irradiation experiments in TAPIRO to support the development of ALFRED, the European demonstrator of the lead-cooled fast reactor (LFR) technology [4]. The outcomes confirmed the attitude of TAPIRO to address these needs, when the removable 60° copper-reflector sector is exploited, replacing it with nuclear-grade lead blocks. This configuration enables dedicated experiments to investigate neutron propagation in lead, quantifying spectral modifications and measuring benchmark integral observables.

Simulations performed with the deterministic ERANOS code have compared the neutronic behavior of TAPIRO and ALFRED through spectral indices and sensitivity coefficients evaluated at multiple irradiation positions. The results demonstrated that the TAPIRO neutron spectra can be precisely tailored to reproduce those of LFR cores, providing benchmark-quality data directly relevant for reactor design and nuclear data validation. MCNP models of TAPIRO corroborated ERANOS predictions, showing excellent agreement upstream of the lead block, and minor deviations (in the 1 keV–1 MeV range) downstream [5]. Sensitivity and uncertainty analyses further revealed that copper cross sections strongly influence key integral parameters. Given the dual role of copper as both a structural and reflecting material in experimental configurations of TAPIRO, even moderate uncertainties propagate into measurable effects on k_{eff} and spectral indices, limiting the representativeness of experiments. ERANOS calculations, using ENDF/B-VIII.0 nuclear data and JEFF-3.3 covariances (the only available at that time) confirmed that the elastic, inelastic, and capture channels of ^{63}Cu and ^{65}Cu are among the dominant contributors to k_{eff} , f_{28}/f_{25} , and f_{37}/f_{25} . For k_{eff} the most influential contributor is the average number of secondary neutrons per fission (ν) of ^{235}U . With all other isotopes/reaction channels

normalized to this reference (100%), the elastic scattering of ^{63}Cu and ^{65}Cu contribute up to 12% and 6%, respectively. For the spectral index f_{37}/f_{25} , the elastic and inelastic reactions of ^{63}Cu account for 67% and 41% relative to the dominant contribution, with ^{65}Cu elastic adding a further 33%. Regarding f_{28}/f_{25} , the inelastic scattering of ^{63}Cu defines the reference (100%), with additional contributions from elastic (54%) and capture (31%) channels. From an uncertainty standpoint, ^{235}U fission is the dominant

Table I. Sensitivity and uncertainty contributions to k_{eff} and two spectral indices from ERANOS calculations using ENDF/B-VIII.0 data and JEFF-3.3 covariances. Values are expressed as percentages relative to the dominant contribution for each observable.

Observable	Relative Sensitivity			Relative Uncertainty		
	Isotope	Reaction	[%]	Isotope	Reaction	[%]
k_{eff}	^{235}U	ν	100	^{235}U	Fission	100
	^{63}Cu	Elastic	12	^{63}Cu	Inelastic	26
	^{65}Cu	Elastic	6	^{63}Cu	Elastic	25
	^{63}Cu	Inelastic	3	^{65}Cu	Elastic	19
	^{63}Cu	Capture	2	^{65}Cu	Inelastic	10
f_{37}/f_{25}	^{237}Np	Fission	100	^{63}Cu	Inelastic	100
	^{63}Cu	Elastic	67	^{65}Cu	Inelastic	34
	^{63}Cu	Inelastic	41	^{63}Cu	Elastic	29
	^{65}Cu	Inelastic	33	^{63}Cu	Capture	17
	^{63}Cu	Capture	32	^{65}Cu	Elastic	16
f_{28}/f_{25}	^{63}Cu	Inelastic	100	^{63}Cu	Inelastic	100
	^{63}Cu	Elastic	54	^{65}Cu	Inelastic	41
	^{65}Cu	Inelastic	39	^{63}Cu	Elastic	16
	^{63}Cu	Capture	31	^{65}Cu	Elastic	13
	^{65}Cu	Elastic	27	^{63}Cu	Capture	12

contributor (100%) for the k_{eff} , while, ^{63}Cu inelastic and elastic reactions contribute significantly (26% and 25%), respectively. These are followed by the elastic (19%) and inelastic (10%) channels of ^{65}Cu . For the spectral indices, the ^{65}Cu inelastic reaction provides a relative contribution of 34% to f_{37}/f_{25} and 41% to f_{28}/f_{25} compared to the dominant uncertainty source, the inelastic scattering of ^{63}Cu , while ^{63}Cu elastic adds 29% and 16% to f_{37}/f_{25} and f_{28}/f_{25} , respectively. It was further demonstrated that the sensitivity profile of k_{eff} lies entirely within the principal energy range of interest for TAPIRO (10^{-3} –10 MeV), thereby confirming the system's strong representativeness for fast-spectrum applications [6].

Complementary MCNP sensitivity studies confirmed the ERANOS results, identifying ^{235}U as the most important isotope to which the k_{eff} is sensitive, followed by ^{63}Cu and ^{65}Cu [7]. Figure 1 shows the normalized sensitivities within the fast-energy range of TAPIRO.

Additional MCNP calculations revealed variations in k_{eff} when the ^{63}Cu or ^{65}Cu evaluations from ENDF/B-VIII.0 were replaced with data from alternative modern libraries (JEFF-3.3, JEFF-4T3, JENDL-5, TENDL-2021, ENDF/B-VIII.1). The reference calculation uses the entire ENDF/B-VIII.0 library yielding $k_{\text{eff}} = 1.00002 \pm 0.00008$. The resulting spread - ranging from 20 pcm to 600 pcm, depending on the library from which the Cu isotope is retrieved - underscores the critical role of precise and accurate copper nuclear data in fast-spectrum analyses. These differences are particularly significant compared to the reactivity worth of the control elements in TAPIRO: ~ 400 pcm for the regulation rod, ~ 1100 pcm for the two combined compensation rods, and ~ 1600 pcm for the two safety rods [8].

Figure 1. Normalized sensitivity profiles for copper isotopes ^{63}Cu (a) and ^{65}Cu (b). The red shaded region highlights the neutron-energy range of interest for TAPIRO.

Table II. Calculated k_{eff} values obtained by replacing the reference copper evaluation for ^{63}Cu and ^{65}Cu with the indicated libraries (1σ Monte Carlo uncertainties) [8].

Cu evaluation (replacing ENDF/B-VIII.0)	$k_{\text{eff}} (^{63}\text{Cu})$	$k_{\text{eff}} (^{65}\text{Cu})$
JEFF-3.3	1.00637 ± 0.00001	0.99980 ± 0.00001
JENDL-5	1.00147 ± 0.00001	0.99782 ± 0.00001
TENDL-2021	1.00102 ± 0.00001	1.00017 ± 0.00001
ENDF/B-VIII.1	1.00342 ± 0.00008	0.99806 ± 0.00008

The effect is more pronounced for ^{63}Cu than for ^{65}Cu - with the exception of JENDL-5 - consistent with the higher isotopic abundance of ^{63}Cu ($\approx 70\%$) in natural copper. The comprehensive qualification and refinement of copper nuclear data are essential to fully exploit TAPIRO's capability as a reference benchmark facility.

3. COMPARATIVE MEASUREMENTS AND EVALUATIONS OF COPPER ISOTOPES

To provide a consolidated overview of the current status of copper cross sections - and to motivate new high-quality measurements aimed at their refinement - a systematic comparison of experimental evidence, reported uncertainties, and evaluated data was performed. This analysis covers the available information for the (n, γ) , (n, n) , (n, n') channels, and the $(n, n'\gamma)$ emission branch of the ^{63}Cu and ^{65}Cu isotopes. The results reveal critical gaps in the experimental foundation, inconsistencies in the treatment of uncertainties, and significant dispersions among modern evaluations, all of which directly affect the reliability of fast-spectrum simulations. Most experimental information originates from transmission measurements available in EXFOR [9], with very limited dedicated elastic-scattering data. Resonance parameters for capture reactions are largely derived from ORELA experiments conducted in the 1970s, complemented by a few more recent high-resolution transmission measurements at GELINA, along with a few additional but dated datasets. Consequently, the elastic channel is typically inferred indirectly from total cross-section data, as the contribution of radiative capture is comparatively minor. The inelastic scattering is particularly underconstrained: only three EXFOR measurements exist (from

1963 and 1970), with no information below 1 MeV and limited data points near 14–15 MeV, typically lacking uncertainty estimates. For discrete inelastic γ -ray production the situation is similar: below 2.9 MeV for ^{63}Cu and 3.2 MeV for ^{65}Cu , only a few datasets are available (Boswell, 2013; Nishimura, 1965), restricted to specific transitions such as the 365.2 keV, 669.62 keV, 770.6 keV, and 1115.546 keV line, and often inconsistent with one another and with evaluated data. Regarding the evaluated nuclear data, the treatment of uncertainties remain uneven. Among modern libraries, only JEFF-3.3 (aside from the most recent JEFF-4.0) provides quantified uncertainties. In this library, relative standard deviations for capture cross sections exceed 10% in the 0.001–0.01 MeV range, and remain within 5–10% from 0.1 MeV up to a few MeV region, while inelastic-scattering uncertainties reach 10–25% between 0.6 and 2 MeV, decreasing to 3–5% at higher energies. Significant discrepancies also persist across libraries: ENDF/B-VIII.0 generally exhibits a richer resonance structure than JEFF-3.3 and JENDL-5.0, particularly in the 50–100 keV interval. In the resolved-resonance region, deviations in the elastic channel can reach 30%, while in the MeV range systematic differences of 10–15% are observed for both isotopes. For inelastic scattering, inter-library differences amount to roughly 15% for ^{63}Cu and 25% for ^{65}Cu , while discrepancies in discrete inelastic γ -ray production channels reach 10–15% below 3 MeV for both isotopes. The comparison thus highlights three key issues:

- scarcity and obsolescence of the experimental basis;
- incomplete and inconsistent covariance treatment of uncertainties across libraries;
- non-negligible spread among evaluations over both resonance and continuum energy ranges.

These findings underscore the need for renewed high-precision high-accuracy energy-dependent cross section measurements and revised evaluations to reduce data-induced biases in reactor physics analyses. Beyond the isotope-resolved datasets, additional insight can be obtained from the EXFOR database for natural copper, which, although not directly comparable with isotopic evaluations, reveals broader systematic trends and persistent discrepancies in elastic scattering. The elastic scattering cross section of natural copper exhibits a pronounced energy dependence, characterized by a highly structured resonance pattern in the epithermal ranges (10^{-4} – 10^{-1} MeV), where values can exceed 100 barn.

Significant discrepancies are observed among the JEFF-2.2, JENDL-4.2, and ENDF/B-V evaluations, with differences reaching factors of up to a factor 2–3 in the resonance region and systematic deviations of 20–30% in the fast-neutron domain (1–100 MeV). Despite the extensive experimental coverage (1956–2006, encompassing data from several authors), the scatter among measurements remains considerable, reflecting the intrinsic experimental challenges associated with this reaction channel. Additional observables, notably the dipole Legendre moment (P_1) of the elastic angular distribution, have been even less extensively investigated. The only available experimental series (Popov, 1986), covering the keV–MeV region, shows broad consistency with ENDF/B-VII and ENDF/B-VIII.1, whereas JENDL-5 deviates from the measured data by up to 10–15

4. NEW MEASUREMENTS OF COPPER CROSS-SECTIONS AT N_TOF (CERN)

Motivated by the analyses here explained, a comprehensive experimental program was launched to improve the nuclear data foundation for copper isotopes, given the role of copper cross sections for the TAPIRO reactor. Within this framework, ENEA triggered an international coordinated initiative, aiming to provide high-precision and high-accuracy measurements of the (n, γ) , (n, n) , and (n, n') reaction channels of ^{63}Cu and ^{65}Cu . To meet these needs, a working group consisting of researchers from ENEA, INFN and other institutes, submitted a proposal at the ISOLDE and Neutron Time-of-Flight Experiments Committee of CERN [10], which was subsequently evaluated and approved.

The experimental campaign encompasses a series of (n, γ) measurements - performed last year - alongside transmission experiments. In parallel, dedicated experimental setups aimed at assessing the feasibility of elastic and inelastic scattering cross-section measurements were deployed at the n_TOF facility at CERN - a high-intensity pulsed neutron spallation source designed for precision measurements of neutron–nucleus interactions over an extremely wide energy range (from the meV region up to several

GeV) [11]. Neutrons are produced by spallation of a 20 GeV/c proton beam on a lead target and their kinetic energy is determined by the time-of-flight. Multiple experimental areas and a variety of detector systems support research programs in nuclear astrophysics, reactor and transmutation technology, and applied nuclear physics, providing high-quality nuclear data.

The $^{63}\text{Cu}(n, \gamma)$ and $^{65}\text{Cu}(n, \gamma)$ experiments were performed using a dedicated array of four C_6D_6 liquid scintillation detectors, symmetrically arranged around the copper target. At the conclusion of the capture campaign, attention turned to the complementary measurement of the total cross section, using a natural copper target. This campaign has now been successfully completed, and the data analysis is currently in progress. Preliminary results reveal high-quality transmission information. In particular, for the first time the total cross section is studied in the neutron energy region between a few meV to tens of MeV. The results of this measurement will serve as the experimental foundation for the resonance shape analysis and forthcoming determination of reaction channel cross sections, including elastic channel.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This work highlights the impact of copper nuclear data on the quality of neutronic simulations of experiments in TAPIRO, thereby supporting the qualification of the TAPIRO fast research reactor as a benchmark facility for fast reactor development.

Analyses performed with ERANOS and MCNP confirmed that the elastic, inelastic, and capture channels of ^{63}Cu and ^{65}Cu strongly affect key observables such as k_{eff} and spectral indices, influencing both the accuracy of integral benchmarks and their representativeness to target fast reactor designs when current evaluations are employed. Copper nuclear data are also expected to affect the effective mean neutron generation time, and improved Cu cross sections would therefore strengthen TAPIRO-based predictions of kinetic observables.

To mitigate these deficiencies, ENEA launched the RAMEN initiative within the framework of the Euratom APRENDE project, in close partnership with the CERN n_TOF Collaboration. The program encompasses targeted analyses that underscored the need for new measurements of the elastic, inelastic, and capture channels for copper isotopes. Capture and transmission campaigns at n_TOF have already been completed, while feasibility studies using stilbene detectors demonstrated the capability of measuring elastic scattering reactions, paving the way for forthcoming (n,n) copper measurements.

The continuation of this program will therefore focus on direct measurements of copper elastic and inelastic scattering, filling one of the most critical nuclear data gaps identified for TAPIRO. In conjunction with refined evaluations and covariance information, these results will significantly enhance the precision and accuracy of copper cross sections.

Such progress will reduce current uncertainties in reactor-physics predictions, increase the representativeness of TAPIRO-based benchmarks, and reinforce the experimental data, improving the reliability of simulations to support the design and safety assessment of advanced fast-spectrum systems. In this way, TAPIRO can extend its scope from a versatile fast-neutron source into a reference benchmark facility, providing high-quality experimental data to support the design and validation of advanced fast reactors. Reviewer: Are the spectral indices mentioned in Section 2 evaluated over the whole core domain?

Authors: ERANOS 2.3 calculations were carried out within Pb-propagation studies for the TAPIRO reactor, with the goal of demonstrating the feasibility of new integral experiments in support of fast-reactor development, including LFRs. In this framework, a 60° sector of the external copper reflector was replaced with nuclear-grade lead. The comparison between TAPIRO and ALFRED was then performed by analyzing the neutron spectra and by evaluating two key spectral indices at selected irradiation positions located on the two sides of the Pb block (upstream and downstream), together with other integral observables. In particular, the feasibility study considers the ($^{238}\text{U}/^{235}\text{U}$, $^{237}\text{Np}/^{235}\text{U}$) spectral indices, evaluated upstream and downstream of the lead block, and correlated with the same quantities in ALFRED at the corresponding locations (up- and down-stream the first ring of sub-assemblies

around the active ALFRED core, which are supposed replaced by pure Lead channels) (see [5]). Further analyses aimed at ranking the relevance of copper nuclear data with respect to the total contributions adopt the same approach and extract the spectral indices at specific, representative locations of the reference configuration, rather than as core-averaged quantities. In this case, the indices are evaluated at points representative of the regions most affected by copper, i.e. at the boundary between the inner and outer copper reflector regions (located upstream of the lead block), where copper-driven spectral shaping and its impact are most significant.

NOMENCLATURE

f_{28}/f_{25} Spectral index based on $^{238}\text{U}(n,f)/^{235}\text{U}(n,f)$

f_{37}/f_{25} Spectral index based on $^{237}\text{Np}(n,f)/^{235}\text{U}(n,f)$

AOSTA Activation of OSMOSE Samples in TAPIRO

APRENDE Addressing Priorities of Evaluated Nuclear Data in Europe (Euratom-funded project)

ERANOS European Reactor ANalysis Optimized System

HPRL High Priority Request List

INTC ISOLDE and Neutron Time-of-Flight Committee (CERN)

ISOLDE Isotope Separator On-Line Device (CERN)

LFR Lead-cooled Fast Reactor

MCNP Monte Carlo N-Particle transport code

n_TOF Neutron Time-of-Flight facility at CERN

OECD/NEA Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development / Nuclear Energy Agency

TAPIRO TARatura Pila Rapida a Potenza 0 - Zero Power Fast Reactor for Calibration

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